

Replication of a Case Study Through the Application of Action Research to Promote Industry-Academia Collaboration

I. GUIDE TO THE QUESTIONNAIRE APPLIED TO CUSTOMERS

Part 1 - Project duration

RQ1: Did the duration of the project positively or negatively influence project execution? For what reason?

RQ2. Over the duration of the project, an MVP (Minimum Viable Product) was produced, what level of satisfaction with the product?

Part 2 – Action Research Assessment

RQ3: In your opinion, the choice of this method (Action Research) was representative for strengthening the ties between academia and industry?

RQ4: Do you believe that industry and government are open to applying this research method?

Part 3 - Challenges and Benefits for Industry/Academia with the application of Action Research

RQ5: With the execution of the project, what are the main benefits of collaboration between academia, government and/or industry?

RQ6: With the execution of the project, what are the main challenges of collaboration between academia, government and/or industry?

RQ7: Did the development team routinely contact you? How often?

RQ8: Was the time you made available to assist developers adequate?

RQ9: What do you suggest to strengthen the relationship between academia, industry and government?

Part4 - Demographic profile of the respondent

RQ10: What is your education level?

RQ11: What is your current job title (Teacher, Director, Programmer, Manager,)?

RQ12: How much experience do you have in your current position?

RQ13: How many years of IT experience (in years)?

RQ14: How old are you?

RQ15: What is your gender?